

A Simple Apparatus for Fractional Solidification.

By R. PADMANABHAN.

In fractionally freezing out a mixture so as to separate it into its components it is found that the efficiency of the separation depends largely on vigorous stirring when solidification takes place. When the experiment is carried out at low temperatures, it is better for the substance to be out of contact with air so that contamination with atmospheric moisture may be prevented. The method described below is found to work satisfactorily in practice and the separation of the solid from the portion still liquid is more efficiently being done *in situ*, while there is no chance for entry of atmospheric moisture.

A is a wide test tube and B an immersion filter which serves also as a stirrer. The cork C is attached to the test tube by a short piece of cycle tubing D, which allows the filter to be moved up and down. The cork also carries a calcium chloride tube and a thermometer. In order to prevent the substance getting into the filter, it is kept filled with some inert gas under slight pressure by its end being connected to a carbon dioxide Kipp. When the material is partially frozen by the tube being immersed in a suitable freezing mixture, suction is applied to the end of the immersion filter till all the unsolidified portion is taken up in the filter and carbon dioxide begins to bubble through. The filter is then slightly raised and the pinch-cock P screwed down. If now the test tube is allowed to warm up to room temperature, the contents can be poured out without any condensation of moisture on the substance taking place.

DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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